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Testing large Optical Systems

Bernhard Braunecker

We explained in Nr. 71 and 72 of this journal special concepts of optical metrology. We apply in this issue the wavefront method WF to verify the optical quality of large optical systems and especially of space telescopes before their launch into space.

Testing the Herschel Telescope

As an example of a large scale WF measurement methodology, we mention the tests performed in 2008 of the big Cassegrain telescope of the Herschel satellite which provided astronomical data in the IR range of 10 - 60 μm in the years from 2009 to 2013. The telescope consisted of a concave parabolic primary mirror of 3.5 m diameter¹ and a convex hyperbolic secondary mirror of about 30 cm diameter, both mirrors made of sintered SiC-100 material and using M93-Cryogenic Invar for all the supporting structures as the spider legs between prime and secondary mirror² (Fig. 1). The correct mirror mounting was tested in a vacuum chamber at University of Liège (BE), where also temperature cycles could be run.

Fig. 1: Herschel Cassegrain Telescope

The correct mirror mounting was tested in a vacuum chamber at University of Liège (BE), where also temperature cycles could be run.

52 liquid mirrors are aligned on optical bench inside the chamber

Fig. 2: The oil pot assembly used as reference mirror

The applied measurement principle was *Autocollimation*, where a laser source is placed at the known back focal point of the telescope and the emitted plane wavefront at the primary mirror is reflected from a plane reference mirror outside the telescope and focused back through the telescope to a 2D-sensor in the nominal focal plane. For cost reasons, however, the plane autoreflexion mirror of 3.5 m diameter was replaced by an arrangement of up to 52 small subapertures in the form of well reflecting oil pots of $D_{\text{Ref}} \sim 20$ cm diameter (Fig. 2).

Since Herschel should be placed in Lagrange point L2, its best focus position had to be checked at 70 K, the temperature at L2. Therefore the oil pot array had to be thermally protected from the cold telescope by thermal shrouds which mechanical apertures were only shortly opened during the

¹ Maximum payload diameter of ESA's Ariane 5 ECA rocket, the space carrier.

² https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Space_Science/Herschel_overview

laser shot. The test results showed surprisingly that the position of the best focus moved by 11.7 mm when cooling down from room temperature to 70 K, and thus significantly exceeded the expected tolerance range of ± 1.6 mm. Since nothing could be changed on the telescope at that time, the only thing left to do was to manually defocus it by -11.7 mm at room temperature, that later in L2 the full spatial resolution should be obtained at 70 K. However, the associated risk could only be addressed if the pre-correction would be constant in time, so it was necessary to understand all the unexpected error sources. Of this error value, 8.5 mm could be explained mainly by insufficient knowledge of thermal material constants³; errors which, however, would be constant in time, while the remaining contribution of 3.2 mm was suspected but not proved to be due to so-called *cryo-quilting*. This effect is observed when the backside of a large mirror is milled out in a cell shape structure for weight reduction reasons. Numerical simulations of the primary mirror construction showed, that the thinned layer of SiC-material over a cell can slightly bend under the applied extreme cooling conditions. This causes many local pseudo-spherical WF distortions which, when added-up, could explain indeed the missing 3.2 mm of defocus.

But is this last value still valid when Herschel reaches L2 after several months of travel? The uncertainty was that these local deformations at 70 K were not confirmed by the measurements due to the too widely spaced oil pots. Therefore there was some remaining risk when defocusing the telescope at room temperature to the full amount of -11.7 mm. Fortunately Herschel later at L2 captured images of the specified full resolution over its entire working period of four years, whereby surely the large IR wavelength was an advantage⁴. Nonetheless ESA asked us if there were alternative solutions to measure the WF gradient at any point inside a large test aperture to avoid the information loss by a fixed arrangement of small subapertures?

Large scale Hartmann WFS

Our idea was to repeat the classical Hartmann test which we described in Nr. 72, where a hole is scanned across a large test aperture. In this case, however, the Hartmann hole is replaced by a 90° prism from the size of an oil pot of small diameter D_{Ref} (Fig. 3), which hypotenuse reflects a well collimated laser beam in z-direction, i.e. into the telescope along its optical axis. The optics focuses the beam on a position sensitive detector PSD, where the position vector $\mathbf{R} = (x, y)$ of the intensity centroid allows to determine the gradient of the transmitted WF. It is a mix of the telescope's optical aberrations which should be measured, and the small deviations of the incident beam direction along the z-axis⁵. The prism is moved in $\mathbf{v} = (u, v)$ direction across the telescope aperture, which unavoidably causes mechanical errors. Any

³ The thermal expansion data of Cryo-Invar at 70 K are extremely low but also slightly shape dependent. Since the material was also used for the sockets in the prime mirror carrying the spider legs, any insecurity of the thermal data can lead by insufficient construction to mechanical tensions and surface distortions, which contribute to the global wavefront deformations.

⁴ https://www.sps.ch/varia/archive/engelberg_lectures_2007
 ⇒ File: WE4_-_Large_Space_Telescopes_v3_Doyle.pdf

⁵ The reconstruction of the WF phase term in the entrance pupil from the measured intensity centroid \mathbf{R} is described in detail in the SPG Mitteilungen Nr. 72 on p. 38. In paraxial approximation the plane WF tilt angle α is obtained from $\tan(\alpha) = \mathbf{R} / F$.

Fig. 3: The prism is moved in \mathbf{v} direction and deflects the collimated laser beam into the telescope. Any angular distortion of the beam leads to a spot displacement \mathbf{R} on the PSD.

displacement errors in $u = x, v = y, z$ are irrelevant, but not the roll error γ around the u -axis and the yaw error α around the v -axis. Both angular distortions are not distinguishable from a WF gradient of the telescope in v -direction, resp. in u -direction.

The scan is performed first in x -direction, called *fast x-scan*. After then the whole platform is moved a small step δy in y -direction, called *slow y-scan*, to run another x -scan. The measurement goal is to monitor the angular distortions of both scans. As illustrated in Fig. 4 the setup consists of two stages, first a platform (blue) carrying the sensor unit with the deflection prism (green circle). A motor moves the sensor unit along the x -direction, while the platform itself is riding on the second stage which moves it in y -direction. Both stages include a stationary autocollimator unit, emitting several laser beams at different wavelengths, and a CCD sensor.

Fig. 4: Measuring the WF across a large test aperture. The motorized platform (blue), moveable in $v=y$ -direction, carries the motorized sensor unit with a deflecting prism (green) and a pentaprism. The blue light from an autocollimator is reflected of the front surface of the pentaprism and backfocused on a CCD to measure the pitch and yaw errors of the mechanical motion. The red light is reflected of a mirror stripe through the pentaprism to measure the roll error. The orange light is reflected by the hypotenuse mirror of a 90° prism into the telescope and focused on the PSD (see Fig. 3).

	Fast scan in x=u direction				Slow scan in y=v direction		
	Offset at PSD	Angular Error	Offset at CCD 1		Angular Error	Offset at CCD 2	
			Prism Reflex	Mirror Reflex		Prism Reflex	Mirror Reflex
WF_x	X_{PSD}	$\alpha_{Yaw,(y)}$	z_{CCD1}/f	-	$\gamma_{Roll,(y)}$	0	x_{CCD2}/f
WF_y	Y_{PSD}	$\gamma_{Roll,(x)}$	0	y_{CCD1}/f	$\alpha_{Yaw,(x)}$	z_{CCD2}/f	-
irrelevant	0	$\beta_{Pitch,(z)}$	(y_{CCD1}/f)	-	$\beta_{Pitch,(z)}$	(x_{CCD2}/f)	-

Table 1: Scanning variant with **fast x-** and **slow y-**scan. The WF errors correspond to a spot on the PSD sensor in the focal plane of the telescope at coordinates $[X_{PSD}, Y_{PSD}] = F [WF_x, WF_y]$ with F focal length of telescope. The reflections of the pentaprisms and of both mirror stripes are measured on the CCDs of both autocollimators with focal length f.

Variant 1 with Mirror Stripes

Parallel to both motorized lead screws a small mirror stripe is permanently mounted to measure the roll errors. A pentaprism is part of the sensor unit which front surface is coated to be reflective for blue light, but transmissive for other wavelengths. When blue light emitted by the autocollimator is reflected from the front surface, one gets the platform's pitch and yaw errors from the spot position on the CCD-sensor, but not the roll error. When red light is emitted which is reflected from the mirror stripes, its spot position on the sensor is now proportional to the roll error⁶. Moving the platform to the next v-position by δv leads to similar roll, pitch and yaw errors but now in y-direction. They must be measured in the same way as in x-direction (Fig. 4).

Table 1 summarizes, that a WF-gradient WF_x (tilt of plane WF around the y-axis) which would lead to an x-offset at the PSD in the focal plane of the telescope, is corrupted twice, first by a yaw angular error $\alpha_{Yaw,(y)}$ of the fast x-scan motion and second by a roll angular error $\gamma_{Roll,(y)}$ of the slow y-scan. Both errors can be measured, the first one as reflex of the front surface of the pentaprism on the CCD 1 of autocollimator1, and the second one as reflex of mirror stripe 2 on the CCD 2 of autocollimator 2. The measurement of the WF-gradient WF_y (tilt of plane WF around the x-axis) is carried out in the same way and shown in the table. We tested recently the concept to measure the roundness of an approximately 1 m long cylindrical drive shaft. The shaft was positioned in x-direction and was scanned with a laser interferometer moving in x-direction and measuring the distance in y-direction.

Variant 2 with Wedge Element

The idea of both mirror stripes as reference surfaces is a huge step forward compared to the use of a large autocollimation plane mirror. Nonetheless it is interesting how to avoid them and what is the price to pay? One idea is to replace the pentaprism by a transparent wedge which double-reflects the laser light (red/green). This leads to two separated focus spots on the CCD of the autocollimator which rotate around the optical axis if the wedge is rotated. The problem is to separate the roll, pitch and yaw errors with sufficient accuracy. Especially critical is to avoid any interference between the reflections from the internal wedge sides. It is surely helpful to install inside the collimator some holographic elements which generate not single spots but patterns on the CCD to detect more easily any rotation.

Fig. 5: The autocollimator emits laser light of different wavelengths (also in time sharing mode) to monitor pitch and yaw from reflections of the blue plate, but also from both sides of the wedge plate (green, red).

Variant 3 with multiple Scan

The following concept was developed by Leica for ESTEC, which also avoids the mirror stripes, but needs a second fast/slow full scan where the scanning setup is rotated by 90° around the z-axes, followed by a single scan with the setup rotated by 45°⁷.

According to Table 1 the elimination of the mirror stripe in the fast x-scan would only allow to measure the WF-gradient WF_x (tilt of plane WF around the y-axis), but not WF_y . Since in the slow y-scan the error $\gamma_{Roll,(y)}$ contribution to WF_x is not measurable without mirror stripe, its amount must be considered as unknown variable in the numerical evaluation.

In mathematical terms a scan in x-direction gives applying eq. (2b) from⁸

$$X_{PSD}(u, v) = \int du' dv' B(u - u', v - v') \delta\psi(u', v') / \delta u' + O_x(v),$$

where the integral is taking over the small diameter of the probe beam D_{Ref} . X_{PSD} is the x-component of the centroid R_{PSD} of the beam on the PSD sensor, corrected with the reading of autocollimator sensor for $\alpha_{Yaw,(y)}$ in the fast x-scan and multiplied by the total intensity $I = \int du dv B(u, v)$. $B(u, v)$ is the beam intensity function, ψ the aberrated WF phase of the telescope optics and $O_x(v)$ the unknown offset of the roll error in slow y-scan.

If the gradient of the WF phase ψ does not vary too much within the beam profile one may write

$$X_{PSD}(u, v) / I = \delta\psi(u, v) / \delta u + o_x(v)$$

6 The metallic mirror stripe can be an arrangement of many short pieces which true angular orientation is measured by independent pre- and post-calibration runs.

7 Investigations and Evaluations on Optical Terminal Test Facilities, ESA-Contract No. 8133/88/NL/PR

8 SPG Mitteilungen Nr. 72, p. 38 'Optical Wavefront Sensing'.

with $o_x(v) = O_x(v)/l$. Integrating this equation with respect to u (i.e. in x -direction), one arrives at

$$\int_0^u du' X_{\text{PSD}}(u', v) / l = \psi(u, v) + o_x(v) \cdot u + c_x(v),$$

where $c_x(v)$ is an unknown integration constant. To eliminate the unknown terms $o_x(v) \cdot u$ and $c_x(v)$, the scan procedure above is repeated after a rotation of the scan setup about the z -axis by 90° . Then the result of this second fast/slow full scan will be

$$\int_0^v dv' Y_{\text{PSD}}(u, v') / l = \psi(u, v) + o_y(u) \cdot v + c_y(u).$$

The difference of the two equations for $\psi(u, v)$ yields an equation of the type:

$$f(u, v) = o_x(v) \cdot u - o_y(u) \cdot v + c_x(v) - c_y(u),$$

where $f(u, v)$ stands for the difference in the left hand sides of the two equations. By e.g. expanding all functions into a power series in u and v , it is seen that this equation determines all unknown functions up to the following terms: $o_x(v)$: $a \cdot v + b$ and $o_y(u)$: $a \cdot u + c$ due to the 90° rotation, $c_x(v)$: $c \cdot v + d$, $c_y(u)$: $b \cdot u + d$, where a, b, c, d are unknown constants. As piston and tilt are not considered ambiguities, the only significant constant is a , the others can be put to zero. That is $\psi(u, v)$ can be determined up to term $a \cdot u \cdot v$ representing astigmatism. It is clear that a single scan with the measurement setup rotated at an angle of 45° will eliminate this last ambiguity.

Stitching Method

Often one only wants to obtain a rough idea of the WF under test. To reduce the time effort, it is advisable to select in a first step large sampling steps δu and δv to obtain a first estimate of the WF of the full aperture by interpolation.

Fig. 6: Stitching concept. The fit of the WF parts inside the six overlap zones allows to eliminate the mechanical driving errors.

This was the concept in the Herschel case with the oil pot array. If the WF results are negative, one can easily repeat the scan with smaller sampling steps. The variable sampling strategy leads to another interesting application, the 'stitching' method, where δx and δy are kept smaller than D_{Ref} , that adjacent WF measurements overlap (Fig. 6).

In a first step the measured WF ψ_0 at sampling point $\mathbf{r}_0 = (x_0, y_0)$ (green circle) is developed as usual according to 24 or 36 Zernike polynomials, and also the WFs ψ_i ($i = 1 \dots 6$) of its adjacent six neighbors (blue circles). But they include the unknown mechanical tilt errors. To get rid of them the Zernike polynomials of ψ_i are numerically shifted by $\delta \mathbf{r}_i = (\delta x_i, \delta y_i)$ with respect to ψ_0 . Then separate best fits are performed

over each of the six central overlap areas using the Zernike polynomials of both ψ_0 and $\psi_i(\mathbf{r}_0 + \delta \mathbf{r}_i)$ to minimize the error functions $F_i = \int \int dx dy [(\psi_i - \psi_0) + a_i + b_i x + c_i y]^2$. The fit results lead to new piston and tilt values (a_i, b_i, c_i) to correct the first three Zernike terms of each $\psi_i(\mathbf{r}_0 + \delta \mathbf{r}_i)$. Finally, a global Zernike fit of ψ_0 and all six corrected ψ_i is performed within the dashed green circle D_{Stitch} . The advantage is that any mechanical tilt errors are eliminated by the algorithm and we obtain from the seven measured WF with small aperture D_{Ref} the full WF over the larger diameter D_{Stitch} ⁹.

Additional Comments

The advantage of the scanning method is that one can easily drive to all critical points as for example to the mentioned spider socket regions or to cell structure boundaries of the Herschel telescope, where higher order aberrations are expected due to thermal tensions. It makes sense to replace the folding mirror in Fig. 4 by a commercially available Shack-Hartmann WF sensor of about 1 inch diameter for local checks and to replace the PSD in the telescope's focal plane by a laser diode. If a thermal shield is needed to isolate the 'cold' telescope from the 'warm' WF scanning units as in the case of Herschel, a mathematical equivalent polar scan (r, ϕ) is better suited than the described cartesian x, y scan¹⁰.

Conclusions

Measuring the WF of large optical apertures is always an engineering challenge, independent what variant is chosen. Highest precision of all components and their mechanical drives are often not sufficient to reach the specified measurement accuracy for space or astronomical applications. Variant 1 needs two mirror stripes, but is a well proved method in daily industrial use, robust and accurate, however critical for larger apertures. Variant 2 is attractive due to its compactness, but sensible to clearly separate the angular distortions and to avoid interferences. The use of holographic elements in the entrance pupil of the autocollimator may be helpful. The advantage of Variant 3 is the simple scanning hardware excluding the roll error measurement. The rotation of the scan set-up by 90° and 45° needs more mechanical effort. In conclusion each variant has its pros/cons and the optimum solution depends on the constraints as size of the aperture, accuracy, thermal environment and speed.

⁹ The stitching method was developed in 1989 at Leica Geosystems in Heerbrugg called WILD LEITZ AG at this time, when our fabrication had to quickly measure a plane mirror of 12 inch diameter. Since the test tool was a WYKO-interferometer of only 6 inch free aperture diameter, we tried the stitching idea. To check the method, we measured first the WF of an existing plane mirror of 6 inch free aperture diameter. Then we manually reduced the aperture diameter of the WYKO-interferometer to 3 inch and moved it according to Fig. 6 to the six adjacent hexagonal positions. From the seven single WF measurements of 3 inch diameter we computed the virtual 6 inch WF and compared it to the direct measurement. The difference was better than $\lambda/10$ pV over 90 % of the 6 inch mirror area. The interesting results were presented at the DGaO Conference in Berlin in 1989. Today the stitching method is a standard option in most commercial interferometers.

¹⁰ The thermal shield would be a rotating disk of special heat reflecting material of the diameter of the large test aperture, including a small radial slit of the width of the measuring subaperture, the Shack-Hartmann sensor.